

FORECASTING THE DEVELOPMENT OF LIVING PLACE AND CATERING SERVICES IN GENERAL

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Abstract: In this article, the theoretical and practical basis of the normative assessment of consumer requirements for improving the quality of accommodation and general catering services for the population in tourism and hotels has been researched.

It is known that one of the methods of forecasting the development of the industry is forecasting using econometric models. Various econometric models are used for forecasting. Including one-equation regression models (one-factor and multi-factor linear), time series models (trend, complex additive forecast model, autoregression model, etc.), in forecasting socio-economic processes from a system of simultaneous equations (independent, recursive, dependent) widely used. In this case, the main requirement is that the model satisfies the conditions of adequacy, while the model should fully preserve the objective nature of the process being studied.

In modern econometric studies, it is common to build forecasting models based on a specific scenario.

A wide range of forecasting methods can be used to calculate forecast values for accommodation and catering development. Among them, the method of econometric modeling, which is part of the method of formalization of forecasting in the exploratory and normative direction, is distinguished by having a number of advantages. The following are the main advantages of forecasting using econometric models:

- calculates forecast indicators at the mega, macro, meso, micro levels of development and fully encourages long-term forecasting;
- constitutes a certain scenario of the development of separate production and industries;
- provides the possibility of multi-variant forecasting;
- has a methodological and technological priority in increasing the

accuracy of forecasting, substantiating its reliability;

- the only method of forecasting complex, stochastic nature, uncertain socio-economic processes.

In general, the econometric approach in forecasting the development of accommodation and public catering services represents the state of development of the network for the previous and current period, analyzes, evaluates the results of planning, evaluates the future state of development based on current trends in the exploratory direction of forecasting, and forecasts the main directions of development based on a normative approach.

Here, the econometric models developed on the basis of various econometric methodologies have the functions of expression, calculation, analysis, comparison, evaluation, determination, optimization in the direction of development and ensure the effectiveness of the research.

With the help of multi-factor linear, trend and ARIMA models constructed using the Gretl program, forecast indicators of the price index in real values compared to 2010 for the main indicator were calculated (Table 1).

Table 1.

Parameters and adequacy indicators of the ARIMA(2,1,2) model for forecasting the volume of residential and catering services in Kashkadarya region

Model 9: ARIMA, used in Ukraine 2002-2021 (T = 20)

Zavisimaya peremennaya: (1-L) VACS

Standartnye oshibki rasschitany na osnove Hessiana

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>St. lover</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>P sign</i>	
const	1.39392	0.512473	2,720	0.0065	***
phi_1	1.18214	0.434336	2,722	0.0065	***
phi_2	-0.742396	0.463642	-1,601	0.1093	
theta_1	-0.990162	0.597459	-1.657	0.0975	*
theta_2	0.882551	0.638580	1,382	0.1670	
Srednee zav. sweets	1.282795		St. ocl. factory	1.664766	
Srednee innovative	is -0.00014		St. ocl. innovative	1.374001	
R-squared	0.980218		Ispr. R-squared	0.976509	
Log. probability	-35.51988		Crete. Akaike	83.03975	
Crete. Schwartz	89.01415		Crete. Hennana-Quinna	84.20602	

	<i>Actual frequency</i>	<i>Mnimaya frequent</i>	<i>is Module</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
AR				
Coren 1	0.7962	-0.8445	1.1606	-0.1297
Coren 2	0.7962	0.8445	1.1606	0.1297
MA				
Coren 1	0.5610	-0.9047	1.0645	-0.1617
Coren 2	0.5610	0.9047	1.0645	0.1617

Table 2.

Results of forecasting the volume of accommodation and public catering services in Kashkadarya region

Forecast years	Volume of residential and catering services of Kashkadarya region, in real values, billion soums (VACS)					
	ARIMA	Growth (%)	trend	Growth (%)	multifactorial	Growth (%)
2022	30,26	6.47	35.60	25,26	33.01	16,15
2023	32.92	8.79	38.76	8.88	36,21	9.69
2024	35,48	7.78	42.06	8.51	39.81	9.94
2025	37,31	5.16	45,49	8.16	43.90	10.27
2026	39.54	5.98	49.06	7.85	48.60	10.71
2027	41.87	5.89	52.76	7.54	53.99	11.09
Average growth rate (%)	6.7		10.9		11.3	
2027 vs. 2021 (equal)	1.47		1.86		1.90	

According to the data of Table 2 presented in the Eviews 10 program, when determining the adequacy indicators of the constructed models and the width of the 95% confidence interval of the forecast values, the relative superiority of the multifactor linear empirical model is noticed. Indeed, the Akaike information criterion for the multivariate linear model is 2.37, the error of approximation is 5.1 percent, and the average width of the confidence interval is 10.01. For these indicators, trend and ARIMA models, respectively, the Akaike information criterion is 52.23 and 83.04, the approximation error is 5.9 and 7.2 percent, and the average width of the confidence interval is 11.6 and 14.0.

Thus, we select the results of the multifactor linear empirical model for the forecast values of the volume of residential and catering services of Kashkadarya region calculated in real values. In that case, the average growth rate of real value of residential and catering services of Kashkadarya region will be 11.3% in the next six years, and it will reach 53.99 billion soums in 2027. This value is equal to 1.9 times compared to 2021.

According to the results of the above assessment of elasticity coefficients, the increase in the volume of residential and catering services of Kashkadarya region in the following years, the increase in the number of items in the network and the amount of basic funds will have a significant impact. Also, the development of the service sector in the region will be one of the most important factors. For this reason, it is possible to determine the trend of changes in the share of accommodation and general catering services in the total services in the following years, to determine new, important, priority directions for the development of the sector.

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